

Jet quenching in evolving media

Xoán Mayo López^{1,*}

¹*Instituto Galego de Física de Altas Enerxías,
Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela 15782, Spain.*

We calculate the radiative soft gluon spectrum from a hard quark in the presence of an inhomogeneous QCD background medium. We take into account multiple soft interactions between the quark+gluon system and the medium. We use a gradient expansion approach, which allows to account for inhomogeneity effects perturbatively. The results show that the gluon's transverse momentum tends to align preferentially along the anisotropy direction.

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Introduction: In the ultra-relativistic heavy-ion collisions a new state of nuclear matter is created, with an energy density so high that quarks and gluons are no longer confined in hadrons but forming a continuous medium. After thermalization, it gets close enough to equilibrium to be understood as a strongly interacting fluid, the so-called quark-gluon plasma (QGP). The QGP exhibits a pronounced collectivity behaving almost as an ideal fluid. The consequent expansion and cooling of the QGP is well understood in terms of relativistic viscous hydrodynamics. Once the energy density is low enough, the nuclear matter becomes confined again and the system turns into a gas of hadrons.

Studying the properties of the color medium through the different phases during its evolution is very interesting due to its sensitivity to color confinement or the origin of hadronic matter, among other fundamental pieces of QCD. In order to do so there are two main sources of information: soft particles originating from the medium after its hadronization, and hard particles originated on the initial hard scattering. The hard probes interact with the medium in a path-length dependent way, losing energy and getting their substructure modified, which makes them good candidates to 'image' the nuclear matter. This concept is the central idea of the so-called jet tomography. For a recent discussion see [1].

Amplitude resummation: A whole formalism to study the

interaction of the jet with medium has been developed over the last 30 years. Both static and longitudinal expanding homogeneous media were considered in different observable and substructure computations. Nevertheless, the effects of velocities and inhomogeneities in the jet transverse plane¹ have been taken into account formally only in [1, 8–11]. In particular, a resummation of multiple interactions with an inhomogeneous dense QCD medium up to leading gradient contributions is done in [9] for the jet momentum broadening. The goal of this work is to extend this result for the leading gradient effects $\mathcal{O}(\nabla/E)$ on the spectrum of the medium-induced radiation to all order in opacity expansion.

Through out the computation we will focus on the transverse gradients of the source density and Debye mass, assuming the matter to be static for simplicity, for the flow effects see [1, 10]. In this limit, following [9], we start with the medium-induced colour field, which reads

$$gA^{a\lambda} = g^{\lambda 0} v(q) \left[\int d^2\mathbf{x} dz e^{-i(\mathbf{q}\cdot\mathbf{x} + q_z z)} \hat{\rho}^a(\mathbf{x}, z) \right] (2\pi) \delta(q^0), \quad (1)$$

where $\rho^a(\mathbf{x}, z)$ is the colour charge density in coordinate space. Here, we use the Gyulassy-Wang (GW) model, and the single-source potential is $v(q) = \frac{g^2}{q^2 - \mu^2 + i\epsilon}$.

The general contribution to the amplitude with N_p interactions with the medium by the mother quark and N_l , N_k interactions by the daughter quark, gluon reads

* xoan.mayo.lopez@usc.es

¹ For earlier attempts to include the flow and gradient effects into probe-medium interactions, see e.g. [2–7]

$$\begin{aligned}
iR_{N_p N_l N_k} &= \int \frac{d^4 p_s}{(2\pi)^4} \prod_{n=1}^{N_p} \left[(-1) \int \frac{d^3 p_n}{(2\pi)^3} t_{proj}^a \rho^a(p_{n+1} - p_n) v(p_{n+1} - p_n) \frac{2E}{p_n^2 + i\epsilon} \right] \\
&\times \prod_{m=1}^{N_l} \left[(-1) \int \frac{d^3 l_m}{(2\pi)^3} t_{proj}^a \rho^a(l_{m+1} - l_m) v(l_{m+1} - l_m) \frac{2(1-x)E}{l_m^2 + i\epsilon} \right] (-1) g_{proj}^a \frac{(p_s + l_{in})_{\mu_1}}{p_s^2 + i\epsilon} (2\pi)^4 \delta^{(4)}(p_s - l_{in} - k_{in}) J(p_1) \\
&\times \prod_{r=1}^{N_k} \left[\left(-\frac{i}{g} \right) \int \frac{d^3 k_r}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{N^{\mu_r \nu_r}}{k_r^2 + i\epsilon} \Gamma_{\nu_r \mu_r + 1 0}^{a_r a_{r+1} c}(k_r, -k_{r+1}) \rho^c(k_{r+1} - k_r) v(k_{r+1} - k_r) \right] \epsilon^{*\mu_{N_k+1}}(k_f)
\end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon^{*\mu_r}$ is the transverse polarisation of the gluon r , $N^{\mu\nu} = \eta^{\mu\nu} - \frac{k^\mu n^\nu + k^\nu n^\mu}{k \cdot n} + n^2 \frac{k^\mu k^\nu}{(k \cdot n)^2}$ is the numerator of the gluon propagator and $\Gamma_{\mu\nu\rho}^{abc}(k, p, q) = g f^{abc} [g^{\mu\nu}(k-p)^\rho + g^{\nu\rho}(k-p)^\mu + g^{\rho\mu}(k-p)^\nu]$ the usual three gluon vertex.

Assuming the soft gluon approximation, the amplitude can be resummed to all orders yielding to

$$\begin{aligned}
iR &\simeq \frac{g}{xE} \int_0^\infty dz_s \int d^2 x_{in} e^{-i\mathbf{x}_{in} \cdot \mathbf{1}_f} J(\mathbf{x}_{in}) \\
&\times \mathcal{W}(\mathbf{x}_{in}; L, z_s) t_{proj}^a \mathcal{W}(\mathbf{x}_{in}; z_s, 0) e^{i \frac{k_f^2}{2xE} L} \\
&\times [\epsilon \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}_{in}} \mathcal{G}^{ba}(\mathbf{k}_f, L; \mathbf{x}_{in}, z_s)],
\end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{W}(\mathbf{x}; z_2, z_1)$ is the usual Wilson line in the fundamental representation defined as

$$\mathcal{W}(\mathbf{x}; z_2, z_1) = \mathcal{P} \exp \left(i \int_{z_1}^{z_2} d\tau t_{proj}^a v^a(\mathbf{x}, \tau) \right) \quad (2)$$

and $\mathcal{G}^{ba}(\mathbf{x}_f, z_2; \mathbf{x}_{in}, z_1)$ is the single-particle propagator

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{G}^{ab}(\mathbf{x}_f, L; \mathbf{x}_{in}, z_s) &= \int_{\mathbf{x}_{in}}^{\mathbf{x}_f} \mathcal{D}\mathbf{r} \exp \left(\frac{ixE}{2} \int_{z_s}^L d\tau \dot{\mathbf{r}}^2 \right) \\
&\times \mathcal{P} \exp \left(-i \int_{z_s}^L d\tau T_{ab}^c v^c(\mathbf{r}(\tau), \tau) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

The next step to compute the spectrum is to square the amplitude, sum over final quantum numbers and average over the initial ones and the medium configuration. After dealing with the colour structure it reads

$$\begin{aligned}
(2\pi)^2 \omega \frac{dN}{d\omega d^2 \mathbf{k}} &\equiv \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{N_c} \sum \int \frac{d^2 \mathbf{l}}{(2\mathbf{p})^2} |R|^2 = \frac{\alpha_s}{N_c \omega^2} \text{Re} \int_0^L d\bar{z} \int_0^{\bar{z}} dz \int_{\mathbf{x}_{in}, \mathbf{y}} |J(\mathbf{x}_{in})|^2 \left[(\nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \cdot \nabla_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}}) \right. \\
&\times \left. \left\langle \mathcal{G}^{bc}(\mathbf{k}, L; \mathbf{y}, \bar{z}) \mathcal{G}^{\dagger ab}(\mathbf{k}, L; \bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{z}) \right\rangle \left\langle \mathcal{G}^{ca}(\mathbf{y}, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}, z) \mathcal{W}_A^{\dagger a\bar{a}}(\mathbf{x}_{in}; \bar{z}, z) \right\rangle \right] \Big|_{\mathbf{x}=\bar{\mathbf{x}}=\mathbf{x}_{in}}. \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

Medium averages: A Gaussian statistics is assumed in order to take the medium average over the scattering centers. As it is explained in [9], the medium average is modified by the effect of gradients. In the particular case of the GW model under the gaussian approximation for the medium and up to the accuracy level being considered throughout this work, the average of two fields reads

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle t_{proj}^a v^a(\mathbf{r}, \tau) t_{proj}^b v^b(\bar{\mathbf{r}}, \bar{\tau}) \rangle &\simeq \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{r}(\tau) + \bar{\mathbf{r}}(\bar{\tau})}{2} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{g}} \right) \\
&\times \mathcal{C} \delta(\tau - \bar{\tau}) \rho g^4 \int \frac{d^2 \mathbf{q}}{(2\pi)^2} \frac{e^{i\mathbf{q} \cdot (\mathbf{r} - \bar{\mathbf{r}})}}{(\mathbf{q}^2 + \mu^2)^2} \quad (4)
\end{aligned}$$

where ρ and μ are assumed to be independent on the longitudinal direction, and the operator $\hat{\mathbf{g}} = \left(\nabla_{\rho} \frac{\delta}{\delta \rho} + \nabla_{\mu^2} \frac{\delta}{\delta \mu^2} \right)$ encodes the information about the

transverse gradients.

The first object of (3) is the 2-point function, related to the momentum broadening and already computed in [9] to first order in gradients. The second object is the so-called radiative kernel

$$\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{y}, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}_{in}, z) = \frac{1}{N_c^2 - 1} \text{Tr} \langle \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{y}, \bar{z}_s; \mathbf{x}_{in}, z) \mathcal{W}^\dagger(\mathbf{x}_{in}; \bar{z}, z) \rangle \quad (5)$$

whose path integral can be solved under the harmonic approximation for the potential and its first order in gradients is obtained by expanding the path integral.

Medium induced spectrum: The medium induced spectrum will be computed under some approximation. First, we are going to compute it perturbatively to first order in gradient expansion and using the harmonic approxi-

mations. Furthermore, we use the broad source approximation $|J(\mathbf{x}_{in})|^2 = \delta^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}_{in})$, so that the initial state effects disappear. We can separate gradient corrections to the medium induced spectrum by its source: the radiative kernel, the broadening distribution or the shift

operator (see [9]). Thus, we can write $(2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} = (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_0}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\mathcal{P}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\mathcal{K}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\hat{S}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}}$ and more explicitly

$$\begin{aligned}
(2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} &= (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_0}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\mathcal{P}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\mathcal{K}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} + (2\pi)^2\omega \frac{dI_{\hat{S}}}{d\omega d^2\mathbf{k}} \\
&\equiv \frac{2\alpha_s C_F}{\omega^2} \Re \int_0^\infty d\bar{z} \int_0^{\bar{z}} dz \int_{\mathbf{y}} e^{-i\mathbf{k}_f \cdot \mathbf{y}} \left[\mathcal{P}_{0;L-\bar{z}}(\mathbf{y}) \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{K}_0(\mathbf{y}, 0, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}, 0, z) + \delta \mathcal{P}_{L-\bar{z}}(\mathbf{y}) \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{K}_0(\mathbf{y}, 0, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}, 0, z) \right. \\
&+ \mathcal{P}_{0;L-\bar{z}}(\mathbf{y}) \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \delta \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{y}, 0, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}, 0, z) + \mathcal{P}_{0;L-\bar{z}}(\mathbf{y}) \left(\left\{ i \frac{(L-\bar{z})^2}{2\omega} \hat{\mathbf{g}}\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{y}) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} - \frac{\mathbf{y}}{2} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{g}}\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{y})(L-\bar{z}) \right\} \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} - \hat{\mathbf{g}}\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{y})(L-\bar{z}) \right) \\
&\left. \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{K}_0(\mathbf{y}, 0, \bar{z}; \mathbf{x}, 0, z) \right]_{\mathbf{x}=\bar{\mathbf{x}}=0} + (\bar{z} > L, 0 < z < L)
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Further analytical expressions are not illustrative due to the size and complexity of the equations. Accurate numerical representations of the spectrum and gradient effects on jet substructure observables are being computed at the moment. Nevertheless, it has been seen as a preliminary result that the effect of leading gradients on the spectrum is to bend the emission along its direction, i.e. they produce an anisotropic emission

$$\langle k^\alpha f(k_\perp^2) \rangle \sim \nabla^\alpha \rho \tag{7}$$

Conclusion: In this work, we have re-summed to all order in opacity the gluon emission spectrum in the presence of finite hydrodynamic gradients. Apart from the qualitative effect mentioned above, more precise results are set to be released soon. The formalism developed here of

highly energetic partons going through a coloured background field could be extended to account the interaction of jets with cold nuclear matter, what may be very useful in deep inelastic scattering for the future EIC.

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